

Relating biodiversity with human population health: an ecological study across England

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GISRUK 2024

Summary

The contribution of biodiversity towards human health provides a convincing argument for a synergistic relationship between the two. Some studies undertaken at the local level indicate the positive effect of biodiversity, however there is a lack of research at larger spatial scales. In this ecological study, we utilise bird, mammal, plant, and population health data. Controlling for confounding factors our results demonstrate a positive but inconsistent relationship with health and mammal occurrence, other biodiversity metrics do not illustrate a significant relationship. Results highlight the volume of mammals may be important for reducing the healthcare burden and increasing wellbeing.

KEYWORDS: Public Health, greenspace, Salutogenic, crowdsourced geographic information, biodiversity

1. Background

While benefits of nature to physical and mental health are well known, research into biodiversity and health are less explored. Biodiversity, serving as an indicator of the genetic, species, and ecosystem diversity across all life forms on Earth, plays a fundamental role as a cornerstone in establishing material underpinnings for physical well-being (WHO, 2015). Some studies have shown a positive effect of biodiversity on human health (Aerts et al., 2018; Marselle et al., 2019). Self reported overall health has been reported to increase with visitation of diverse urban parks (Carrus et al., 2015), similarly self reported “good” overall health prevalence was observed among people living in areas of higher bird species richness (Wheeler et al., 2015). These studies use objective measures for species richness based on ecological monitoring schemes and occur at a local or city-wide scale. In general, there is a limited amount of empirical evidence available regarding the influence of biodiversity, whether it is positive or negative, on physical health (Sandifer et al., 2015) particularly on a larger spatial coverage. To enhance our comprehension of the broadness of the association between biodiversity and human health, it is imperative to conduct epidemiological studies on a larger spatial scale with additional measures of biodiversity including mammal and plant diversity. This study will help identify pertinent relationships and build the evidence base essential for the development of effective local and national policies, in addition to land management strategies.

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2. Methods

2.1 Data

This is an ecological study across England where the spatial unit is at the local authority district (LAD) level, with two main areas of data: 1) species richness and occurrence of bird, mammal and plants as indicators of county level biodiversity, and 2) count-level statistics of population health. In addition, characteristics of the population, macro-economic and geographical local in England by local authority were also included for potential confounding adjustment.

Public health data is to be taken from the Office for National Statistics in the form of the recently established Health Index. The index covers a broad definition of health including domains, health outcomes, health-related behaviours and personal circumstances, and wider drivers of health that relate to the areas that people reside (Office for National Statistics, 2023). The index provides a single value for health that can illustrate changes over time. The Health Index is comprised of 56 indicators, summarised into 14 subdomains, 3 domains and then an overall score for each geographical area in this study at LAD level (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The 2021 England Health Index compared to 2015 baseline.

Biodiversity data has been acquired from the National Biodiversity Network (NBN) Atlas. The NBN Atlas is an online tool launched to share biological data and improve environmental knowledge, through improving the availability and quality of biodiversity data and records and enhance the evidence base for national decision making. NBN engages organisations and citizen scientists to report biological observations using standard protocols to facilitate this mission. Biodiversity data including bird, mammal and plant species richness and occurrence for the year 2021 was acquired from the NBN atlas and aggregated to LAD level (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Mammal, bird and plant species richness data at LAD level.

The following macro-economic factors that may influence human health were also taken into account: population density, Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita, unemployment rate and local authority area size (km²) and education level. All Macro-economic variables are measured at the LAD level. Macro-economic variables have been made available by the ONS.

It has been shown greenspace or protected area cover influence human health in epidemiological studies (Wheeler et al., 2015). Blue space, and atmospheric temperature are also thought to impact health and wellbeing (de Vries et al., 2016; Yu et al., 2012) as such are included as adjusting factors. Auxiliary datasets describing environmental characteristics including biodiversity have been chosen based on literature and past studies. Table 2 describes independent variables and their sources used in this study.

Table 1: Independent variables considered in this study.

Variable Category	Independent Variable	Source
Macroeconomic	Income deprivation (2019) GDP per capita	Office for National Statistics
Demographic	Population density Education level	Office for National Statistics
Health	England Health Index	Office for National Statistics
Environmental	Greenspace % Blue space % Protected areas %	UKCEH Landcover Natural England
	Normalised Difference Vegetation Index variance Area	MODIS Office for National Statistics
	Average temperature	MODIS Terra Land Surface Temperature
Biodiversity	Elevation range Bird, mammal, plant species richness	SRTM Digital Elevation National Biodiversity Network Atlas
	Bird, mammal plant occurrences	

2.2 Empirical analysis

Initially testing for global spatial autocorrelation for the health index produced a significant Moran's I statistic of 0.19, indicating ideally a spatial model should be used.

To examine the association of biodiversity measures and the health index, we used linear regression (ordinary least squares, OLS (with heteroscedasticity robust standard errors), spatial error and spatial lag models. Comparing models allows for comparison and validation, while accounting for various macro-economic, demographic and natural factors. To avoid multicollinearity issues each model contained only two species diversity variables. To identify and reduce multicollinearity we calculated variance inflation factor and correlation. The following control variables with VIF scores >10 were excluded from our final models (Dormann et al., 2013). For use in spatial models a spatial matrix using queens contiguity was implemented.

After model fitting, the associated *p-value* for each covariate indicates the statistical significance of each independent variable. If the *p-value* is below 0.05, a statistically significant association between the dependent and independent variable is classified. Figure 3 illustrates the designated workflow for the study.

Figure 3: Association study workflow.

3. Results and discussion

At time of writing analysis is ongoing. Initial results indicate agreement between OLS and spatial lag model but disagreement with spatial error model. Calculation of Akaike Information Criterion for each model indicates the lowest value for the spatial lag model AIC = 1801 (Mammal model) and AIC= 1804 (Bird model), indicating this model fits the data the best of the three types. In all spatial lag models, no biodiversity metrics hold a significant effect to the health index, however notably across all models income deprivation (-1.98, CI=-2.18, -1.79), GDP per capita (-0.00003, -0.00005, -0.00001), and apprenticeship education (-0.00035, -0.00058, -0.00013) negatively associated with general health. While level 4 education (0.00004, 0.00001, 0.00007) has a small positive association with the 2021 Health Index. As few studies using the England health index exist, results from this work could impact authority and national level decision making to facilitate widescale health interventions. Presenting at GISRUK would allow scrutiny from a wider pool of academia, as an early-stage research student this would be invaluable to ensure further aspects of biodiversity - health links are considered.

4. Limitations

One caveat in our study is related to the spatial scale of our study where we use England local authority boundaries as a unit to describe people's experienced environment, as this was the finest resolution at which information was available for many variables across England but particularly the Health Index. As the Health Index is an experimental metric, a smaller spatial unit is not currently available. As a consequence, there might be a pronounced local variation in species richness and other nature characteristics within each county, which can influence estimated confidence intervals in our results. However, future work may use more established health metrics with smaller spatial units such as the Indices of Multiple Deprivation Health domain or attempt to reduce the coarseness of the Health Index through modelling. Additionally, as an ecological study this work will not indicate causal mechanisms, there is a plausible mechanism suggesting that this association is meaningful.

5. Conclusions and Future Works

- Utilising other techniques to validate results will be required including Bayesian inference and random forest Model Class Reliance.
- Utilising other metrics of public health at a smaller spatial scale to establish the existence of a health-biodiversity relationship.
- The project outputs will contribute towards the wider evidence base of biodiversity contributing towards public health. Implications of this work include evidence building for informative policy making into national scale health interventions and potential reduction of the public health burden.
- The project uses largely open datasets, meaning techniques can be applied to other areas of interest for future comparative studies or when new data become available. Comparison in this way will help indicate the contextual nature of the biodiversity-health relationship in different national regions.

Acknowledgements

This research was funded by EPSRC Geospatial Systems CDT. Special thanks to Dr. Sabrina Li at University of Nottingham Faculty of Social Sciences for analysis advice and continued support. Biodiversity taken from National Biodiversity Network: available from: <https://nbnatlas.org/>

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Biographies

Philip Home is early-stage PhD student at the University of Nottingham and Newcastle, as a 3rd cohort member of the EPSRC Geospatial Systems CDT. Philip has a BSc in Environmental Science, an MSc in Risk and Disaster Science, and an MRes in Geospatial Data Science from the University of Nottingham. His research interests include nature's contribution to people, data visualisation/storytelling and using spatial data to inform effective decision making.

Dr. Sabrina Li is Assistant Professor in Quantitative Geography at the University of Nottingham. Sabrina's research investigates the interactions between human health and the physical, social, and built environments. In particular, She is interested in understanding why certain populations are more susceptible to diseases and ill health than others, and the assessment of differential health impacts experienced by disadvantaged populations. Most of her work focuses on the social and environmental determinants of health. To address the complexity of these research areas, she utilises large spatial data

sets and tools from GIS and quantitative methods.

Doreen Boyd is Professor of Earth Observation with research interests in using cutting-edge geospatial data science on standard and novel data streams. The principal data stream is that captured by remote sensing systems. Applications cut across a range of UN SDGs, attracting over £10 million in research funding.